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Numerical solution of a class of fractional convection-diffusion equations using bivariate Müntz wavelets

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Abstract

This paper presents a new computational technique for the solution of a class of fractional convection-diffusion equations. The method is based upon the bivariate Müntz-Legendre wavelets; these wavelets are first introduced. Operational matrix of fractional-order integration with the collocation points are utilized to reduce the solution of under study problem to a system of algebraic equations.

Keywords: Bivariate Müntz-Legendre wavelets, Fractional convection-diffusion equations, Caputo derivative.

MSC(2010): 35R11, 34K28, 65M70

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus is an old mathematical topic from the 17th century. It has shown its potential of modeling practical problems in many fields. In general, most of fractional differential equations do not have exact solutions. So, in the last few years, some scientists have devoted to study the numerical solution of fractional differential equations and dynamic systems containing fractional

derivatives, and have proposed several efficient numerical methods such as, least square [1], fractional Bernoulli wavelets [2] etc. In this paper we shall construct bivariate wavelet bases of Müntz-Legendre. These wavelet bases are suitable for numerical solutions of fractional partial differential equations.

Definition 1: The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\alpha \geq 0$ is defined as [3]

$$I^\alpha f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-\alpha}} ds, & \alpha > 0, t > 0, \\ f(t), & \alpha = 0. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2: Caputo's fractional derivative of order α is defined as [3]

$$D^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{\alpha+1-n}} ds, \quad n-1 < \alpha \leq n, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For the Caputo derivative we have

$$D^\alpha I^\alpha f(t) = f(t), \quad I^\alpha D^\alpha f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

2 Bivariate Müntz-Legendre wavelets

The bivariate Müntz-Legendre wavelets are defined on $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ as

$$\Psi_{n,m,n',m'}(x,t) = \begin{cases} (2\lambda_m + 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} (2\lambda_{m'} + 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} 2^{\frac{k+k'}{2}-1} L_m(2^{k-1}x - \hat{n}) L_{m'}(2^{k'-1}t - \tilde{n}), \\ \quad \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq x < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{\tilde{n}}{2^{k'-1}} \leq t < \frac{\tilde{n}+1}{2^{k'-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

where $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M-1; m' = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M'-1; \hat{n} = n-1, \tilde{n} = n'-1, n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}; n' = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k'-1}$ and $\hat{m} = 2^{k-1}M; \tilde{m} = 2^{k'-1}M'$. Here, $L_m(x)$ and $L_{m'}(t)$ are the Müntz-Legendre functions which are defined on the interval $[0, 1]$ and $[0, 1]$, respectively, by [4]

$$L_m(x) = \sum_{s=0}^m c_{s,m} x^{\lambda_s}, \quad c_{s,m} = \frac{\prod_{j=0}^{m-1} (\lambda_s + \lambda_j + 1)}{\prod_{j=0, j \neq s}^m (\lambda_s - \lambda_j)}, \quad (m \in \mathbb{N}_0), \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$L_{m'}(t) = \sum_{s'=0}^{m'} c'_{s',m'} t^{\lambda_{s'}}, \quad c'_{s',m'} = \frac{\prod_{j=0}^{m'-1} (\lambda_{s'} + \lambda_j + 1)}{\prod_{j=0, j \neq s'}^{m'} (\lambda_{s'} - \lambda_j)}, \quad (m' \in \mathbb{N}_0). \quad (2.3)$$

These functions satisfy the following orthogonality condition [4]:

$$\int_0^1 L_n(x) L_m(x) dx = \frac{\delta_{n,m}}{(2\lambda_m + 1)}, \quad (m \geq n).$$

Also, the bivariate Müntz-Legendre functions are defined on $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ as:

$$L_{m,n}(x,t) = \sum_{s'=0}^{m'} \sum_{s=0}^m c_{s,m} c'_{s',m'} x^{\lambda_s} t^{\lambda_{s'}}. \quad (2.4)$$

bivariate Müntz-Legendre functions satisfy the following orthogonality condition:

$$\int_0^1 \int_0^1 L_{m,m'}(x,t)L_{n,n'}(x,t)dxdt = \frac{\delta_{m',n'}\delta_{m,n}}{(2\lambda_m+1)(2\lambda_{m'}+1)}. \quad (2.5)$$

bivariate Müntz-Legendre wavelets $\Psi_{n,m,n',m'}(x,t)$ are orthogonal with each other as:

$$\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \Psi_{n,m,n',m'}(x,t)\Psi_{i,j,i',j'}(x,t)dxdt = \delta_{n,i}\delta_{m,j}\delta_{n',i'}\delta_{m',j'}, \quad (2.6)$$

where $\delta_{n,m}$ is the Kronecker symbol.

In this paper, we assume that $\lambda_k = k\gamma$, where γ is a real constant.

3 Operational matrix of fractional integral

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integration of the vector $\Psi(x,t)$ can be expressed by:

$$I_x^\alpha \Psi(x,t) = Q(x,\alpha)\Psi(x,t) = (P_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}}(x,\alpha) \otimes I_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}})\Psi(x,t), \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$I_t^\beta \Psi(x,t) = Q'(t,\beta)\Psi(x,t) = (I_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}} \otimes P'_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}}(t,\beta))\Psi(x,t), \quad (3.2)$$

where I is identity matrix; $Q(x,\alpha)$ and $Q'(t,\beta)$ are $(\hat{m}\hat{m}) \times (\hat{m}\hat{m})$ fractional integration operational matrices of bivariate Müntz-Legendre wavelets, such that $P(x,\alpha)$ and $P'(t,\beta)$ are the fractional integration operational matrices of Müntz-Legendre wavelets defined on $[0,1)$ and $[0,1)$, respectively, as follows [4]:

$$P(x,\alpha) = \Theta^{-1}F(x,\alpha)\Theta, \quad (3.3)$$

and

$$P'(t,\beta) = \Theta^{-1}F'(t,\beta)\Theta, \quad (3.4)$$

where Θ^{-1} is the transformation matrix of the Müntz-Legendre wavelets to the piecewise fractional-order Taylor functions [4].

4 Problem statement and numerical method

We consider the following fractional convection-diffusion equation

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha u(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha} + a(x)\frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x} + b(x)\frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = f(x,t), \quad 0 \leq x,t < 1, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad (4.1)$$

with initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x,0) = f_0(x), \quad u(0,t) = g_0(t), \quad u(1,t) = g_1(t). \quad (4.2)$$

For solving this problem, we approximate

$$\frac{\partial^{2+\alpha} u(x,t)}{\partial x^2 \partial t^\alpha} \simeq C^T \Psi(x,t), \quad (4.3)$$

where $C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{\hat{m}\hat{m}-1}]$ is an unknown vector which should be found. By fractional integration of order α of Eq. (4.3) with respect to t , we get

$$\frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \simeq C^T Q'(t, \alpha) \Psi(x,t) + \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \Big|_{t=0} = C^T Q'(t, \alpha) \Psi(x,t) + \frac{\partial^2 f_0(x)}{\partial x^2}. \quad (4.4)$$

By fractional integration of order 2 of Eq. (4.3) with respect to x , and using Eq. (4.2) we have

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha u(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha} \simeq C^T Q(x, 2) \Psi(x,t) - x(C^T Q(1, 2) \Psi(1,t)) + (1-x) \frac{\partial^\alpha g_0(t)}{\partial t^\alpha} + x \frac{\partial^\alpha g_1(t)}{\partial t^\alpha}. \quad (4.5)$$

By fractional integration of order 2 of Eq. (4.4) with respect to x and considering Eq. (4.2), we get

$$u(x,t) \simeq C^T Q'(t, \alpha) Q(x, 2) \Psi(x,t) - x(C^T Q'(t, \alpha) Q(1, 2) \Psi(1,t)) + H(x,t), \quad (4.6)$$

where

$$H(x,t) = g_0(t) + f_0(x) - f_0(0) - x f_0'(0) + x(g_1(t) - g_0(t)) + x(-f_0(1) + f_0(0) + f_0'(0)).$$

By fractional differentiation of order 1 of Eq. (4.6) with respect to x , we obtain

$$\frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x} \simeq C^T Q'(t, \alpha) Q(x, 1) \Psi(x,t) - (C^T Q'(t, \alpha) Q(1, 2) \Psi(1,t)) + \frac{\partial H(x,t)}{\partial x}. \quad (4.7)$$

Replacing Eqs. (4.4) - (4.7) in Eq. (4.1) and collocating this equation at the zeros of shifted Legendre polynomials $P_{2^{k-1}M}(x)$ and $P_{2^{k-1}M}(t)$ ($x_i, t_j, i = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}M; j = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}M'$).

5 Illustrative test problems

Example 1: Consider the following time-fractional diffusion equation ([5])

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha u(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha} - \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = 2\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(3-\alpha)} t^{2-\alpha} - 1\right), \quad 0 \leq x, t < 1, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad (5.1)$$

where $u(0,t) = t^2$, $u(1,t) = 1 + t^2$, $u(x,0) = x^2$. The exact solution to this problem is $u(x,t) = x^2 + t^2$. By solving this problem for $k = k' = 2, M = M' = 1, \gamma = \alpha$ we obtain the exact solution.

Table 1: Comparison of absolute error for $\alpha = 0.5, t = 0.25$ for Example 1.

x	Ref.[5]		Our method $k = k' = 2, M = M' = 1$
	$J = 1, m = 3$	$J = 2, m = 2$	
0.2	4.4×10^{-3}	8.8×10^{-2}	0
0.4	5.1×10^{-2}	9.8×10^{-2}	0
0.6	7.1×10^{-2}	3.4×10^{-1}	0
0.8	2.8×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-1}	0

Example 2: Consider the initial boundary values problem of fractional partial differential equation of order α ([6], [7])

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha u(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha} + x \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = 2t^\alpha + 2x^2 + 2, \quad 0 \leq x, t < 1, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad (5.2)$$

where $u(0,t) = 2 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} t^{2\alpha}$, $u(1,t) = 1 + 2 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} t^{2\alpha}$, $u(x,0) = x^2$. The exact solution to this problem is $u(x,t) = x^2 + 2 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} t^{2\alpha}$. By solving this problem for $k = 2, M = 1$ we obtain the exact solution.

Table 1: Comparison of absolute error for $\alpha = 0.5, t = 0.5, \gamma = \alpha$ for Example 2.

x	Ref. [6] $m = 64$	Ref. [7] $m = 25$	Our method $k = k' = 2, M = M' = 1$
0.1	1.2×10^{-3}	6.5×10^{-6}	0
0.2	1.3×10^{-3}	1.7×10^{-4}	0
0.3	1.9×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-5}	0
0.4	7.4×10^{-3}	2.9×10^{-4}	0
0.5	1.0×10^{-6}	2.8×10^{-5}	0
0.6	7.5×10^{-3}	2.8×10^{-4}	0
0.7	1.7×10^{-3}	2.0×10^{-5}	0
0.8	5.0×10^{-3}	1.4×10^{-4}	0
0.9	1.7×10^{-2}	4.7×10^{-6}	0

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